

Rac-3a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-80-1-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0731
Vial:	70	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 80 1 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/31/2021 9:07:00 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/31/2021 9:43:57 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.485	19523556	49.17	1894280
2	8.386	20183065	50.83	1740736

Asy-3a (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-80-3-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0731
Vial:	71	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 80 3
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/31/2021 9:22:41 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/31/2021 9:41:10 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.477	508138	3.79	52035
2	8.371	12914679	96.21	1152832

Asy-3a (KR)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-82-p-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0802
Vial:	119	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 82 P
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/2/2021 8:07:04 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/2/2021 8:24:34 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.375	820077	3.81	83742
2	8.241	20685313	96.19	1850116